

Kinetics and Mechanism of Acid Hydrolysis of Di-6-bromo-2,4-dichlorophenyl Phosphate

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Hydrolysis of di-6-bromo-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate has been pursued in HCl (0.03-7M) in dioxan water (16%) at 90°. Ionic strength data upto 3 μ , requires the participation of neutral (I) as well as conjugate acid (II) forms. The slopes exhibit a fixed contribution irrespective of the value of μ . Unimolecular behaviour for the neutral form has been decided by temperature effect studies. Unusual presence of (I) alone has also been highlighted beyond 4M, where the maximum appears as usual. II, however, hydrolyses bimolecularly via monoester formation. Mirror method calculation are helpful to eliminate monoester formation during acid hydrolysis. Solvent isotope effect study favours specific acid catalysis. The diester involves P-O bond rupture which is strengthened by comparative kinetic data.

KINETIC study of the hydrolysis of di-6-bromo-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate has been made for its mechanistic details in the mineral acid range 0.03 to 7 M HCl at 90°, in 16% dioxan-water (for solubility reasons). Concentration of the diester was maintained as $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ throughout the kinetic investigations. First-order rate coefficients have been evaluated using integrated form of the corresponding rate equation. Estimation of the progressive formation of inorganic phosphate as one of the final products during hydrolysis of the present diester was carried out colorimetrically by Allen's modified method¹. In the present paper, the nature of acid catalysis, types of participating reactive species and their modes of hydrolyses have been discussed and the most plausible routes proposed on the basis of available kinetic data. Various correlation plots have also been used to support the tentative routes of hydrolysis.

Experimental

6-Bromo-derivative of 2,4-dichlorophenol was prepared following the method of Fox and Turner². 6-Bromo-2,4-dichlorophenol (5 g) was then dissolved in dry benzene (10 ml) and PCl₅ (2.15 g) was added to it gradually in the ratio 2:1 (w/w) with continuous stirring for nearly 10 h. Subsequent steam distillation of benzene from the reaction mixture left a white solid residue. The residue was dissolved in NaOH (5%) and reprecipitated with HCl (2N). The unreacted phenol was removed by petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and finally the solid recrystallised from CCl₄ yielded pure diester, m.p. 213° (Found: C, 26.89; H, 1.42; P, 5.67. Requires C, 26.38; H, 0.92; P, 5.67%).

All reagents used were of AnalaR or Sarabhai (GR) quality.

Results and Discussion

The first-order rate coefficients for the hydrolysis of the present diester in the range 0.03 to 7M HCl are found to increase with the increase in acid upto 4 M (Table 1). At this characteristic³ acid molarity (4 M) it exhibits a maximum rate which may be ascribed to the presence of increased percentage of singly protonated form of the diester. The rates pass through a minimum at 0.1M where maximum cleavage of neutral form occurs, beyond 4 M the rates decrease.

TABLE 1—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED RATE COEFFICIENTS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF DI-6-BROMO-2,4-DICHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT 90°

HCl M	$10^4 K_{H^+} C_{H^+}$ min ⁻¹	$10^4 K_N$ min ⁻¹	$10^4 K_{cataly}$ min ⁻¹	$10^4 K_{obs}$ min ⁻¹
0.03	—	0.23	0.23	0.24
0.04	—	0.23	0.23	0.25
0.05	—	0.24	0.24	0.28
0.10	—	0.24	0.24	0.26
0.20	0.20	0.26	0.46	0.50
0.30	0.30	0.27	0.57	0.59
0.40	0.40	0.29	0.69	0.69
0.50	0.50	0.31	0.81	0.83
1.00	1.00	0.42	1.42	1.32
2.00	2.00	0.76	2.76	2.39
2.50	2.50	1.03	3.53	3.93
3.00	3.00	1.39	4.39	4.29
4.00	4.00	2.53	6.53	6.25
4.50	—	3.42	3.42	3.45
5.00	—	4.62	3.23 ^a	3.49
6.00	—	8.43	3.19 ^b	2.80
7.00	—	15.38	2.24 ^c	2.27

a, b, c—n in (aH₂O)_n is 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Neutral electrolyte effect study has been performed at different constant ionic strengths using mixtures of HCl and NaCl. The increase in rates

with the increase in acid concentration (Fig. 1) at each ionic strength (μ) indicates specific acid catalysis. This is further supported by the fact that the rates are slightly increased ($K_{D_2O}/K_{H_2O}=1.1$) when water is replaced by D_2O . This also suggests a fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer generally observed for acid-catalysed reactions. Neutral rates are subject to a +ve ionic strength effect, since increase in intercepts with increase in μ has been observed (Fig. 1). Constant slopes of the linear curves (Fig. 1) suggest a +ve but constant contribution of ionic strength effect to the acid-catalysed species (Fig. 2). Similar behaviour has

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis of di-6-bromo-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at constant ionic strengths in 16% dioxan-water at 90°.

Fig. 2. Hydrolysis of di-6-bromo-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at 90°.

been observed for the acid-catalysed hydrolysis of methyl phosphate⁴. From this neutral electrolyte effect study, the total rates contributed by both neutral and conjugate acid forms have been calculated by the following 2nd empirical term of Debye-Hückel⁵ equation.

$$K_e = K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} + K_N = K_{HO^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \exp b_{H^+} \mu + K_{NO} \cdot \exp b_N \mu \quad (i)$$

where K_{H^+} , K_{HO^+} and b_{H^+} are specific acid-catalysed rate at that ionic strength, specific acid-catalysed rate at zero ionic strength and constant, respectively. Similarly, K_N , K_{NO} and b_N are specific neutral rate at that ionic strength, specific neutral rate at zero ionic strength and constant, respectively (Table 1).

Between 0.03 to 0.1M, the rates agree closely and are contributed by only neutral form in equation (i), of the diester. In the range 0.2 to 4M HCl, the close concordance is due to the contribution of both the neutral and conjugate acid species. The maximum at 4M shows incomplete protonation of the diester suggesting its moderately basic nature. Beyond 4.5 M, the calculations are based on the following modified equation of Bronsted-Bjerrum⁶ type using water activity term and considering the participation of the neutral form only.

$$K_e = K_{NO} \exp b_N \mu (a_{H_2O})_n \quad (ii)$$

Beyond 4M, the lowering may be attributed to the total absence of the contribution due to the more reactive conjugate acid form and this can be accounted for by the extensive contribution of only neutral form (less reactive) of the diester. Decrease³ in water activity with increase in acid molarity may also be responsible for such a decline in rates.

The high magnitude of Arrhenius parameters⁷ (Table 2) favours a unimolecular pathway of hydrolysis for the contributory neutral form involving the transition state of highly polar nature. The +ve value of entropy may be understood in terms of steric blocking due to the bulky ortho-bromo substituents coming closer together in two aryl matrices (structure A) due to free rotation about a single bond. Another possibility is the

TABLE 2—CALCULATED ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS IN THE ACID RANGE

HCl M	E kcal mol ⁻¹	A sec ⁻²	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.	ΔG^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹
0.5	34.99	1.00×10^{16}	+13.16	+30.21
3.0	36.61	3.82×10^{17}	+20.92	+32.68
4.0	33.72	2.30×10^{16}	+13.71	+28.73
5.0	35.43	1.35×10^{17}	+17.30	+29.15

stabilisation of the diester due to hydrogen bonding (structures B, C and D), blocking way of the entering nucleophile, water (Chart 1).

Solvent effect studies ($K_e = 13.37 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ in 56% dioxan at 4M) as well as Hammond's postulate⁸ also favour a more polar transition state⁹. Dioxan-water mixtures being better proton-donating¹⁰

Chart 1

media than water alone will, therefore, increase the rates by stabilising 6-bromo-2,4-dichloro phenoxide ions formed during unimolecular hydrolysis of the neutral form.

The hydrolysis of the present diester follows first-order kinetics as the rates at 4M are found to remain unaltered by varying the concentration to either half ($K_e = 6.26 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) or double ($K_e = 6.30 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) the normal concentration ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$).

Hammett¹¹ (0.54), Zücker-Hammett¹² (1.1) and Bunnett⁸ ($w=8.0$ and $w^*=2.6$) plots (not shown) are in favour of a bimolecular pathway for the conjugate acid form. Bunnett-Olsen¹³ parameters ϕ as 1.63 (>0.58) suggests that water acts as a proton transfer agent too. Hydration parameter¹⁴ treatment ($r=1.36$) based on available H_2O data, requires the interference of at least one water molecule leading to the formation of a transition state during hydrolysis. Hammett-Taft¹⁵ relationship plot data ($\rho=+0.72$) recommends electron-withdrawal ($-I$) by halogens (Br and Cl) present in the diester. This perturbation is also evident from the order of acid-catalysed rates (Table 3) and suggests that the diester hydrolyses largely as its undissociated form. Isokinetic relationship¹⁶ plot (not shown) with $\beta=215.5K$ and comparative kinetic data (Table 3) combined with above data support bimolecular mechanism for the conjugate acid form, involving P-O bond rupture. P-O

Chart 2—Unimolecular heterolysis of the neutral form.

Mono-6-bromo-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate

Chart 3—Nucleophilic bimolecular hydrolysis via the conjugate acid (II) from.

TABLE 3—COMPARATIVE KINETIC DATA FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF HALOGEN SUBSTITUTED DIPHENYL PHOSPHATE ESTERS

Sl. no.	Diesters	Temp. °C	$10^5 K_{HO^+}$ sec ⁻¹	Maxima HCl M	E kcal mol ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] e. u.	Fission
1.	Phenyl ^a	100	—	4*	20.8	27.9	P-O [†]
2.	p-Cl ^b	80	6.93	4*	10.6	65.0	P-O
3.	p-Br ^c	98	0.22	4.5*	20.1	30.0	P-O
4.	2,4-di-Cl ^d	98	4.30	3.5	16.6	33.9	P-O
5.	2,4,6-tri-Cl ^e	90	3.03	2.5	34.4	11.9	P-O
6.	2,4,6-tri-Br ^f	98	4.40	4	26.1	7.1	P-O
7.	6-Br-2,4-di-Cl ^g	90	1.70	4	33.7	-13.7	P-O

* HClO₄. † Fission determined experimentally.

^a Ref. 6. ^b S. Deobhakta, Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, 1968. ^c M. M. Mhala, M. D. Patwardhan and G. Kasturi, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 149. ^d S. S. Bhatwadekar, Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, 1972. ^e A. Chaturvedi, Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, 1981. ^f S. Chaudhari, Ph.D. Thesis, Jiwaji University, 1947. ^g This work.

fission leads to the formation of substituted phenoxide ions as stable intermediates.

Lastly, at low acid molarity the rates calculated by mirror method⁶ ($0.30 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 0.1M) closely resemble the experimentally observed rates ($0.26 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) for the diester suggesting the absence of monoester formation during its hydrolysis. Similar calculations when tried at a higher acid molarity, 3M, yield intermediate value of rate data, indirectly pointing out the hydrolysis of conjugate acid form to proceed via monoester formation. Thus the hydrolysis of the diester proceeds in the two ways via two reactive species (Charts 2 and 3).

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